

OPTIMIZATION AND IMPORTANCE OF ULTRASOUND DIAGNOSTIC METHODS IN THE CHOICE OF TREATMENT TACTICS FOR PATIENTS WITH CERVICAL OSTEOCHONDROSIS

Usarov M.S.

Free candidate for the Department of Neurology
Samarkand State Medical University

Djurabekova A.T.

MD, Professor of the Department of Neurology
Samarkand State Medical University

Khamidov O.A.

Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor
Samarkand State Medical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13960404>

Abstract: Degenerative diseases of the spine and spinal cord injury of the cervical spine are an urgent problem of radiology, neurology, neurosurgery and traumatology due to their widespread occurrence, progressive growth over the past 20-30 years and the involvement mainly of people of working age. Symptoms of osteochondrosis are found in 80% of people, and in half of the cases — in the cervical spine.

Keywords: cervical osteochondrosis, neurology, ultrasonography (USG), ultrasound diagnostics (ultrasound).

Introduction. The cervical spine is the most mobile part of the spine, but also the most vulnerable. Vulnerability is associated with anatomical features — a weak muscular corset in the neck area, as well as the small size and low mechanical strength of the vertebrae. To understand at what stage of development the disease is, which structures of the spinal column and which tissues are damaged, various diagnostic methods help the doctor. With a high level of morbidity, duration and severity of clinical manifestations, ineffective conservative treatment is often due to incomplete diagnosis. In this pathology, ultrasonography (USG) and ultrasound diagnostics (ultrasound) have long been used as an effective screening method. The basis of spinal ultrasound is anterior through disk access. When using it, the intervertebral disc, the spinal canal in its median and lateral sections, lateral canals, stenosis, occlusion, deformity and abnormalities of the arteries, and insufficiency of collateral circulation are available for assessment. The combination of diseases of various types, supplemented by osteochondrosis of the cervical spine, significantly exacerbates vertebral basilar insufficiency. Of particular importance is the study of early clinical forms of cerebral pathology, which include the initial manifestations of insufficient blood supply to the brain and dyscirculatory encephalopathy of the 1st stage. An important role in the detection of these conditions is played by the use of ultrasound angiography, which, according to numerous studies, makes it possible to detect morphological changes in 16% of patients in various extra- and intracranial arteries in the form of tortuosity, deformation, hypoplasia of the vertebral arteries, multiple stenoses that worsen the volume and velocity characteristics of blood flow. This group is closely related to persons with asymptomatic forms of vascular diseases, which make up 31.2% of practically healthy individuals, using well-proven methods of ultrasound Doppler diagnostics and guided by the achievements of classical neurology, it is possible to develop a system of clinical diagnostic

search and dynamic assessment of the mechanisms of formation of cerebral circulatory insufficiency in patients with degenerative dystrophic diseases of the spine. The asymmetry of blood flow, which is constantly detected by Dopplerography in patients with manifestations of cervical osteochondrosis, is the subject of special attention. Taking into account the risk of possible complications in the treatment of such patients, a thorough examination before treatment with mandatory clinical and neurological examination and assessment of vascular status by Doppler techniques is a guarantee that the risk of complications will be minimized.

Conclusions. Thus, ultrasound scanning of the vertebral arteries in the extra- and intracranial sections makes it possible to identify with a high degree of reliability the existing circulatory disorders in the vertebral-basilar system. Duplex scanning of vertebral arteries with a rotary probe in extracranial segments is a highly informative technique in the diagnosis of circulatory disorders in the vertebral artery system with the possibility of detecting the level of extravasal compression, especially in the case of diagnosis of vertebral artery syndrome (SPA), including in pediatric practice. This modification of the sample can be recommended as a screening test, both to determine the scope of further examination of the patient, and to identify risk groups for the development of cerebral circulatory disorders in the vertebrobasillary basin. We also consider it advisable to use it as a means of controlling the restoration of blood flow during treatment, as the most accessible diagnostic method.

References:

1. Abelskaya I.S., Begun I.V. Radiological semiotics and hemodynamic parameters in patients with osteochondrosis of the cervical spine // Medical imaging. 2007. No. 4. pp. 91-99.
2. Beletsky A.V., Pustovoitenko V.T., Makarevich S.V. et al. Radiometry of the cervical spine. Minsk: Belarus. 2010. 132 p.
3. Vereshchagin N.V. Pathology of the vertebral-basilar system and disorders of cerebral circulation. Moscow: Medicine. 1980. 312 p.
4. Gorokhova E.N. Clinic, diagnosis and surgical treatment of multiple injuries of the cervical spine of degenerative-dystrophic and traumatic genesis: Abstract. ... candidate of Medical Sciences: 14.00.28 / N.V. Sklifosovsky Research Institute of Emergency Medicine. Moscow. 2008. 32 p.